

Speculation on the Importance of the Constraint Used in Maximizing Tsallis Entropy

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Feb. 1, 2025

In the traditional approach of maximizing entropy subject to a constraint, the constraint form is naturally very important. If, however, one uses time reversal balance and conservation of energy for two body scattering assuming that $f(e_1)f(e_2)$ is the probability for an e_1 and e_2 particle to scatter (Maxwell-Boltzmann) case, then there is no concept of entropy and no concept of a constraint. Using $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ and $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$ yields $f(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$. One may then use experimental data to try to find T and then obtain C through normalization. In other words, a scattering approach does not depend on any notion of a constraint whatsoever.

One may consider a generalized set of equations: $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ and $G(f(e_1)) G(f(e_2)) = G(f(e_3)) G(f(e_4))$. This occurs, for example, in the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases, where G depends on the physics of the reaction (e.g. fermion and boson restrictions). We have argued in previous notes that if one postulates that $d \ln(G(f)) = df f^{-q}$, then one may obtain the Tsallis entropy by considering $P(f) d \ln(G(f)) = df$ and writing $S = \sum_i P(f(e_i)) \ln(G(f(e_i)))$. Given a Tsallis entropy, one would naturally try to maximize it subject to a constraint as discussed in (1). We argue, however, that one does not need any notion of entropy or constraint as: $\ln(G(f)) = \int (1/f) ds s^{-q}$. This leads to $\ln_q(f)$ (the analogue of \ln) such that f should be its inverse function, i.e. the Tsallis probability form: $f(e_i)$ proportional to $\{ 1 - (1-q) a (e_i - u) \}^{-1/(1-q)}$ ((1)). In other words, no notion of a constraint is needed.

We stress the point that no constraint or entropy maximization subject to a constraint is needed to obtain $f(e_i)$ because in (1), ((1)) is obtained by maximizing Tsallis entropy subject to a specific constraint: $\sum_i (e_i - u) p_i (power\ q) = 0$. ((2)) This same constraint is then used when considering Sanov's theorem which contains the Gibbs-Boltzmann (Shannon) entropy. A maximization is performed using the constraint ((2)) to obtain a distribution: P_i proportional to $\exp(b (e_i - u) P_i^{q-1})$. (1) then shows that in many cases P_i and f_i (the Tsallis form) do not coincide. We argue here that P_i is obtained by considering a constraint which does not need to exist if one considers a Tsallis process strictly in terms of collisions. If there is no such concept of entropy and constraint and one still has a Tsallis distribution ((1)) from scattering arguments, then it is not clear why one would create a P_i using a constraint which is not needed to create ((1)), we argue.

Tsallis Entropy and Distribution

Just as in the case of Shannon's entropy and the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, there is no requirement that one create an entropy function and maximize it subject to a constraint. For this case, one may simply use:

$$E_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{and} \quad f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((3b))$$

((3a)) is a statement of conservation of energy and ((3b)) is a specific assumption of the requirement for a successful collision to occur. From these, one has:

$$f(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((4))$$

One may find relative $f(e_i)$ values experimentally and calculate T . One may then find C as a normalization. Thus, it seems that there is no need for any notion of entropy, its maximization or constraint. (Of course, one may introduce these, but one may find the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution without them).

Generalization to the Tsallis Case

We next try to generalize to create the Tsallis case. As a first step, we consider the equations:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((5a)) \quad \text{and} \quad G(f(e_1)) G(f(e_2)) = G(f(e_3)) G(f(e_4)) \quad ((5b))$$

The key idea here is some kind of time reversal balance. For the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases, $G(f(e_i))$ is not $f(e_i)$ as in the MB case. Thus, one may postulate various $G(f(e_i))$ scenarios. One such scenario is:

$$d \ln(G(f)) = df f^{-q} \quad ((6))$$

Integrating the RHS from 1 to f , yields: $\{ f^{-q} - 1 \} / \{-q\}$

This postulate has the feature that if one uses $S = \sum_i P_i(f(e_i)) \ln(G(f(e_i)))$, and the generalizes the property of Shannon's entropy

$$- \sum_i P_i \ln(P_i) = - \sum_i P_i \ln(f) \quad ((7))$$

that Tsallis entropy is: $\sum_i P_i^{-q} \{ f^{-q} - 1 \} / \{-q\} \quad ((8))$

One, however, has no need of entropy. One may use:

$\ln(G(f)) = \{ f^{-q} - 1 \} / \{-q\} = \ln_q(f)$ and seek an inverse function to \ln_q because:

$$\ln(G(f)) = \text{constant } e_i \quad ((9))$$

Thus: $f(e_i) = C \{ 1 - (1-q) a (e_i - u) \}^{-1/(1-q)} \quad ((10))$

This function is obtained with no notion of entropy or its maximization subject to a constraint. If one wished to introduce the entropy ((8)), then a corresponding constraint which yields ((10)) is:

$$\sum_i (e_i - u) P_i^{-q} = 0 \quad ((11))$$

We argue, however, that no constraint or entropy formalism is needed. We suggest that this idea may be important because of the role that the constraint ((11)) plays in (1).

Finding an Asymptotic Distribution in (1)

The key idea in (1) seems to be that using the constraint ((11)) in a maximization scheme using Sanov's theorem leads to the probability distribution:

$$P_i \text{ proportional to } \exp\{-1/T (e_i - u) P_i^{\text{power } q-1}\} \quad ((12))$$

In (1) it is shown through various examples that P_i in ((12)) does not equal the Tsallis $f(e_i)$ distribution ((10)) in many cases and so it is cautioned that one has a problem, namely that "novel entropy functions may give results which are at variance with actual sample frequencies" except in some cases. The form ((12)), however, depends on the use of the particular constraint ((11)). We argue, however, that neither a Tsallis entropy function nor constraint ((11)) are needed to obtain the Tsallis probability function: ((10)). If there is no constraint, then it cannot be used to obtain P_i ((12)).

Conclusion

In conclusion, when maximizing an entropy expression subject to a constraint, the constraint is key in determining the probability distribution. We argue, however, that one may obtain a probability distribution directly from two body elastic scattering in the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases. No notion of entropy, a constraint or maximization of entropy subject to a constraint are needed. In particular, one may use: $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ and $G(f(e_1)) G(f(e_2)) = G(f(e_3)) G(f(e_4))$. If one postulates that: $d \ln(G(f)) = df f^{\text{power } -q}$ (and calls this the Tsallis scenario), then $\ln(G(f)) = -e/T = \ln_q(f) = \{ f^{\text{power } (1-q)} - 1 \} / \{ 1-q \}$. One may then argue that $f_i = f(e_i)$ is simply the inverse function of \ln_q , namely: $f(e_i) = C \{ 1 - (1-q) a (e_i - u) \}^{\text{power } 1/(1-q)}$. This may then be fit to experimental data.

We stress that no constraint is needed even though one may formulate the Tsallis entropy $S = \sum_i P_i \ln(G(f(e_i)))$ such that $P_i = f_i^{\text{power } q}$ (by imposing $P_i d \ln(G(f)) = df$) and then introduce a constraint: $\sum_i (e_i - u) f_i^{\text{power } q} = 0$. In other words, we suggest that one does not need to focus on a constraint. In (1), a maximization process of Shannon's entropy in Sanov's theorem, together with the Tsallis constraint, is used to obtain a probability distribution which differs from the Tsallis one in many cases. This result depends entirely on the constraint used. We suggest that if no constraint is used (i.e. exists) to obtain the Tsallis probability result through scattering analysis, then there would be no need to obtain a different P_i using a constraint.

References

1. LaCour, B. and Schieve, W. A Comment on the Tsallis Maximum Entropy Principle (2018) <https://arxiv.org/pdf/cond-mat/0009216>